

WEBSITE-BASED BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN INCREASING SALES: A STUDY ON THE "RATU HIJAB" BUSINESSES OF SOUTH SULAWESI - INDONESIA**Fitrianti¹, Muhammad Rakib^{2*}, Agus Syam³**^{1,2,3} Department of Business and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri, Makassar, Indonesia*Corresponding Author: m.rakib@unm.ac.id**ABSTRACT**

This research aims to implement a website to increase sales and make it easier for consumers of "Ratu Hijab" business in Takalar Regency. The research method used is Research and Development with a qualitative descriptive approach. The research process for designing this business model adopts a 4D development model consisting of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the study show that a website designed with design and features such as easy navigation and attractive content is able to expand marketing reach and increase sales conversion. The results of the design that have been prepared in such a way are tested by media experts to assess the design of the business model that has been designed by the researcher. After expert testing, the results of the business model design can be recommended for "Ratu Hijab" business to develop her business.

Keywords:

Business Implementation, Website Design, Landing Page, Website Features, Sales Improvement

INTRODUCTION

The development of the internet today is making a great influence in the business world. Information technology makes business processes easy to overcome the fierce competition in the business world. One of the current developments in information technology is the application of websites and the application of e-commerce to help market products and services offered by companies in the business world. With the existence of a website and the application of e-commerce in a company, it will have a great impact on the company, especially in the field of product marketing.

The current development of the internet has changed the paradigm of offline trading activities. Product marketing via the internet is a unique opportunity for entrepreneurs along with the entry of the internet into all levels of society (Anggita, 2023). Along with the advancement of time, technology is not a strange thing for the Indonesian population. The increasingly sophisticated information and communication technology, people not only use it to exchange information, news, and other things, but information and communication technology is also useful for marketing products or services for business advancement. Not only has an impact on social life, digitalization today is also spreading to the business world. This era is an effort to transform from a business that is run conventionally to a business that is run online. (Putra & Diana, 2020)

The manual recording model is considered inefficient in presenting information (Sukerti, 2017). Some of the disadvantages of the conventional transaction recording model include requiring high costs, inhibition in the presentation of information, controlling, and a fairly high risk of data loss (Rahayu & Hermawan, 2020). The development of business in the era of digitalization is described with speed and precision. Digital marketing has been used by several business people, both MSMEs and large companies. The advantage of digital marketing is that products are delivered faster to customers and only require a small amount of money to carry out promotions. With this, an efficient business will be created. (Lailia & Dwiridotjahjono, 2023)

Promotional media using a website is a form of technology utilization that is also considered good for an agency. By implementing a website-based business, sellers can increase sales turnover and expand product marketing. A website is a collection of digital pages that contain information in the form of text, animation, images, sounds and videos or a combination of all that are connected via the internet, so that it can be accessed by all or anyone who can connect to the internet network. (Rukmana & Rohman, 2022)

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In this business case, the researcher only focused on the sales services of “Ratu Hijab”’s business. “Ratu Hijab” is located in Kale Bentang Village, South Galesong District, Takalar Regency. “Ratu Hijab” is a business engaged in fashion, especially hijab. This business offers a wide range of hijabs, ranging from rectangular hijabs, instant hijabs, and pashmina. The hijab sold has several variations of different materials such as a rectangular hijab made of double hycont, pollycotton or double ciffon, while pashmina uses softer materials such as jersey, rayon and babydoll. “Ratu Hijab” was established in November 2022 and is still running and has been proven by a Business Identification Number (NIB). The business is still conventional and has not used technology to the fullest. Meanwhile, based on the results of observations and initial interviews in the field, budget preparation, marketing content creation, and the use of social media are still minimal. The application of a website-based business to “Ratu Hijab”’s business in South Galesong District, Takalar Regency is a strategic step to overcome existing problems, as well as take advantage of the opportunities that exist in the digital era. The main reason for this research is to be able to face the problems that have been described previously and produce a new design recommendation based on the results of the website design.

Based on the above background, the formulation of the problem in this study is how to apply a website-based business in increasing sales in “Ratu Hijab”’s business in South Galesong District, Takalar Regency.

The purpose of this study is to find out the application of website-based business in increasing sales in “Ratu Hijab”’s business in South Galesong District, Takalar Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship

The term entrepreneurship consists of two syllables: hero and business. Business means an activity by exerting energy, mind, or body (institution) to achieve an intention, work (deeds, initiatives, efforts, efforts to achieve an intention, activities in the field of trade (by making a profit), trade, company. (Rakib et al., 2018)

Entrepreneurship is a discipline that studies values, abilities and behaviors in facing various life challenges. Entrepreneurship is taught as a discipline because entrepreneurship has a complete and tangible body of knowledge, has two concepts, namely venture start-up and venture growth, and has its own object, namely the ability to create something (Syam, 2017). Entrepreneurial literacy is also known as entrepreneurial skills. has a crucial role in the success of a business (Majir, 2021). The higher the level of entrepreneurial skills a person has, the easier it is for them to achieve success in the business they are running (Yani et al., 2020). An entrepreneur always has and tries to improve his abilities, in accordance with the opinion (Rakib, 2010) that an entrepreneur who wants to succeed in managing and improving his business performance must have effective communication skills.

Business Implementation

A business model is a method of doing business that is used by a company to be able to maintain its business and be able to generate revenue. A business model describes how a company makes money by determining where it stands in the value chain. A business model refers to a choice in a business model where a company competes in the market (Hidayah et al., 2023).

Website

Websites are one of the internet resources that are growing rapidly with popular information storage media today. The web presents information so that it can display information in various data formats such as text, images, and even videos that can be accessed using various clients. In the application of digital media in the form of websites, namely:

Website Design

According to Suyanto (2007) website design is the art and process of creating a single or entire web page and can involve the aesthetics and mechanical intricacies of a website operation even though the main thing is to focus on the look and feel of the website. While the aspects that include web design include creating animations and graphics, color selection, graphics and fonts (Syam et al., 2024).

Landing Page Website

Landing pages are a driver of revenue and business efficiency or can be referred to as a "money" page. In online marketing, landing pages are needed to increase sales conversions. A landing page is a page that focuses on only one goal. Landing pages are usually equipped with sales letters, product photos and videos, explanations of features, benefits, and various other advantages of a product.

Website Features

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The header is the top component of a website, usually a logo and a navigation menu, the navigation menu is a link that directs users to move to other pages. Usually this saved menu is prioritized to be visited by the user. Logos are usually stored on the left and it is easy to notice the arrangement of the menu from left to right based on its importance. The navigation menu varies from website to website depending on what features are needed by the user or what features the company wants to highlight so that users can see it.

Hero serves as a visitor attraction when he first opens the website. This is why it is usually located on the front or landing page, so this can be displayed among other things such as images or designs that are interesting to see. The footer, which is located at the bottom of the website, is almost the same as the navigation menu, but there are more and more complete. Usually in the footer there is a main menu link, Secondary menu, social media information, Registration form, Email subscription and App download information. White space in a website is certainly not all areas filled with content. There is an empty area that gives distance to the elements and this empty area called white space functions so that the design looks more spacious and users will focus more on the content in the website.

Sales

Sales is the purchase of something (goods or services) from one party to another party by getting compensation from that party. Sales are a source of company income, the greater the sales, the greater the income received by the company. The purpose of sales is to bring profits or profits from products or goods produced by producers with good management.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is Research and Development (R&D) with a qualitative descriptive approach. Research and Development (R&D) is a process or step to develop a new product or improve an existing product, for which it can be held accountable. This research was carried out on the business of "Ratu Hijab" located in Bontobawi, Kale Bentang Village, South Galesong District, Takalar Regency, South Sulawesi. The research was conducted for one month starting from September 2 to October 2, 2024.

The object of research is what will be researched in research activities. In this study, what is used as an object by the researcher is a business engaged in the fashion sector called "Ratu Hijab". The subject of this study uses informants or people who are used to provide information about the situation and conditions of the research background. The subjects of this study are the owners and employees of the "Ratu Hijab" business.

The data sources used in this study are primary data and secondary data, namely: Primary data is information collected directly from business owners obtained through direct interviews with business owners. While secondary data is additional information obtained through literature studies. To gain knowledge and theoretical foundations about the problem to be researched, as well as the acquisition of literature that discusses the research methodology that has been used.

This research procedure adopts from the 4D development model, namely the Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate stages. The define stage is carried out by observation and interview methods with business owners to analyze the problem. Additional data is obtained through documentation of business activities. Then an analysis of the needs and desires of owners and employees is carried out. The design stage is designed with a business model in the form of a website based on the results of the interview. The develop stage is carried out by experts in the media to evaluate the results of the business model design regarding the feasibility provided by "Ratu Hijab"'s business. The disseminate stage will be disseminated the results of the business model design by interested parties.

The data collection techniques used include observation, interviews, and documentation. Observations and interviews are conducted with business owners and employees, as well as documentation to attach evidence that they have conducted research. For data analysis, the Miles and Huberman model analysis technique was used which included data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawn.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results

"Ratu Hijab" is one of the hijab businesses engaged in fashion, especially hijab. This business was established in November 2022 and has been proven with a Business Identification Number (NIB). "Ratu Hijab" offers several products such as rectangular hijab, instant hijab, and pashmina. The hijab sold has several variations of different materials such as a rectangular

hijab made of double hycont, pollycotton or double ciffon, while pashmina uses softer materials such as jersey, rayon and babydoll.

“Ratu Hijab” current business operational process includes customer service, marketing, and financial management. Based on the current operational process of “Ratu Hijab” business, there are several problems, namely customer service, marketing, and financial management. The problem is that “Ratu Hijab” has not been able to adapt to the era of globalization which utilizes technology in serving online, marketing through social media, and has not applied technology in its financial management so that the operational process is hampered. In addition, another problem is competition between several hijab entrepreneurs who have competitive qualifications and have applied technology in marketing and financial management. Therefore, designing a business model is a solution to re-evaluate the state of “Ratu Hijab” business with its needs and desires and improve its services and business sales, especially in the use of technology. In increasing sales from the business, the application of website-based digital media is carried out which includes website design, website landing pages, and website features.

Website Design

Website design is used to include how the web content is displayed. Website design is very important to support consumers to access features so that they linger on the web by providing features and quality of design presentation that are not boring and more attractive. The design of this website will be the main source for consumers to access what “Ratu Hijab” sells and offers.

Landing Page Website

The landing page of this website is to promote “Ratu Hijab” products with an attractive appearance, inviting visitors to explore the product easily and providing several features that make interaction easier. In addition, the landing page also explains the products and types of “hijab” available on the “Ratu Hijab” Queen and also offers direct connections to social media, giving potential customers access to the latest information and product reviews through platforms such as Instagram.

Figure 1. Landing Page of “Ratu Hijab” Website

Website Features

This website feature is very important to be needed in website digital media because this feature provides four parts, namely Navigation, Header, Content or Content and Footer. The Navigation section serves as a guide for visitors to access various pages of the website. Navigation is located at the top or side of the page and contains links to other pages within the site, such as home, products, orders, and contacts. The goal is to make it easier for visitors to find the information they need quickly.

Figure 2. Navigation Page of the “Ratu Hijab” Website

The header serves as the opening element of the website in which there is a logo and business title. The goal is to introduce the website to visitors and make an interesting first impression.

Figure 3. Header Display of “Ratu Hijab” Website

The content (content) aims to provide information that wants to be conveyed to visitors according to what has been provided in the Header.

Figure 4. Content Display of the “Ratu Hijab” Website

The footer is located at the very bottom of the website page and contains contact information, links to social media and the location of the “Ratu Hijab” business. The goal is to provide important information that visitors need, such as how to contact or find additional information about the “RatuHijab” business.

Figure 5. Footer Display of “Ratu Hijab” Website

Research and Development (R&D) Methods

The application of the business model is carried out using the following 4D research procedures.

Define

Based on the identification of pre-research regarding the problems of “Ratu Hijab” business, namely competition and the optimal use of technology so that the purpose of determining it is to implement a website-based business model so that this business can develop in the future. Fierce business competition can encourage the thinking of company owners to think creatively and innovatively so that they are able to compete in the market. Business competition can encourage economic growth by forcing companies to continue to innovate and improve the quality of products and services.

Economic growth is related to developments in the era of globalization, namely the use of modern technology. The development of modern technology is an obstacle for companies to find it difficult to adapt to the current era. Of course, to adapt to the modern era, it is necessary to utilize technology to generate greater income. In this case, “Ratu Hijab” must be able to adapt to modern technology in the face of competition with the method of designing a business model according to the desired desires.

“Ratu Hijab” employees said that there are several shortcomings and uniqueness found in this business. The shortcomings of “Ratu Hijab” business were revealed to be not too active in promoting her business, lack of updates and less varied content. The uniqueness of this business is that the quality is good, the price is affordable, reliable and affordable. Based on the results of interviews with employees, “Ratu Hijab” must use digital media to promote and continue to innovate for attractive product displays, expand market reach and improve financial management. Based on the identification of pre-research regarding the problems of “Ratu Hijab”’s business, namely competition and the lack of optimal digital media so that the goal is to implement a website-based business so that this business can develop in the future.

Design

Based on the results of the definition of the identification of problems from the “Ratu Hijab” business, a website design will be carried out.

Website Design

Website design is the process of designing the layout, appearance and functionality of a website. The design of the “Ratu Hijab” website will use soft colors that reflect an elegant and simple style that suits the hijab products offered. The selection of clear and easy-to-read fonts, with an elegant and simple writing style, to make visitors comfortable when reading product descriptions or other information.

Landing Page Website

The landing page is the first page that visitors see when opening the “Ratu Hijab” website. “Ratu Hijab”’s landing page features special offers, such as best-selling products and the placement of call-to-action buttons, such as "View Collection" to make it easier for visitors to make purchases. In addition, the landing page also displays elements such as a picture of someone wearing a Hijab “Ratu Hijab” product, a brief description and customer testimonials.

Website Features

Website features are elements that support website functionality and provide a better experience for visitors.

Navigation

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Navigation is an important part located at the top of the page, allowing visitors to easily search for various pages or sections so that they are not confused looking for information. The navigation menus designed by the Queen of Hijab are such as Home, Products, Orders and Contacts.

Header

The header is the top part of every website page after the Navigation which is also first seen by visitors like the brand logo. The “Ratu Hijab” logo will be placed in the upper left part of the Header and the name of the business will be placed in the center of the Header.

Contents (Content)

The content is the central part of every page that contains information that you want to convey to visitors. The content of “Ratu Hijab” will feature the hijabs that are sold. Each hijab will be given a full description of the materials, sizes and colors available to help visitors make a purchase decision.

Footer

The footer is the bottom part of the website page that contains important information that visitors need. The “Ratu Hijab” footer contains contact information such as addresses, phone numbers and social media icons such as Instagram to make it easier for visitors to contact if they need more information.

Develop

Sourced from the design of the implementation of a website-based business that has been designed, the next is the development stage. The development stage is carried out by means of expert tests by media experts and stages for “Ratu Hijab” efforts to develop her business in implementing the website that has been designed. After designing the website, the results of the implementation design were assessed by media experts to assess the website that had been created as recommended for the “Ratu Hijab”. The website assessment was carried out by Mr. Dr. Valentino Aris, S. Kom., M.M. The expert is a lecturer as well as an expert in website design. The purpose of the assessment of media experts is to find out whether the implementation of the website is feasible to be implemented by the “Ratu Hijab” business or not. The assessment of the media experts who designed the website can be recommended by the efforts of “Ratu Hijab”. However, according to the expert, the design of the website needs to be improved with a more attractive design and a landing page added so that visitors can easily find out about the description of “Ratu Hijab” products.

Disseminate

Dissemination is the last stage in the Research and Development (R&D) method with a 4D model. This last stage is the dissemination of research results to “Ratu Hijab” business owners so that “Ratu Hijab” can implement or apply the website design that has been prepared by the researcher. Researchers can show the results of the website design for the Hijab Queen. Business owners can consider the results of the researcher's website design to be applied to their business in order to increase sales of their business. The results of this research are also written in the form of scientific papers, theses and journals will then be published online so that the results of this research can be used as a reference by researchers or other business actors who are interested in developing a business through the application of a website-based business.

Discussion

This research designed a website-based business. In this study, the website was used to evaluate how the website can affect the increase in sales of “Ratu Hijab” business. To design the website in this study, the researcher first identified the changes that occurred before and after the implementation of the website consisting of website design, website landing page and website features based on the collection of data obtained from the results of interviews with the interviewees.

The identification of “Ratu Hijab” current business condition shows that the marketing and sales process is still carried out conventionally through social media such as Instagram, WhatsApp and direct communication with customers. This makes the product information conveyed ineffective and reduces efficiency in handling orders. The results of the initial identification are compiled and then evaluated to find out their needs and desires. Then, from the results of the identification of needs and desires, it was found that “Ratu Hijab”'s business experienced obstacles in delivering information and an inefficient ordering process. The identification after the implementation of the website is described below.

Identify the website design of the “Ratu Hijab” business based on needs and desires, including (1) Attractive appearance. (2) Clear structure and easy to navigate. (3) Use of colors that match the brand identity. (4) Suitable layout for various devices. The identification of the website landing page of the “Ratu Hijab” business is (1) Clear content about hijab products. (2) Attractive visuals such as product photos. (3) Direct links to social media for easy interaction. (4) Effective call-to-action (CTA)

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to increase visitor conversion into customers. The identification of website features of “Ratu Hijab” business is (1) Search feature to make it easier for visitors to find products. (2) Integration with chat apps like WhatsApp. (3) Easily accessible price list and location.

The final results of the study show that the implementation of a website-based business that is designed is more in accordance with the needs and desires, so it is expected to increase sales of “Ratu Hijab” business. The implementation of this website-based business is carried out using a 4D development procedure from four stages, namely Define, Design, Develop and Dissaminate.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research on “Ratu Hijab”’s business as described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that the results of the implementation of the website have provided changes to business development. The website designed with design, landing page and features has provided convenience in marketing strategies and increased operational efficiency of “Ratu Hijab”’s business. With the existence of a website, product information can be conveyed more clearly and visitors’ access to products becomes easier, thereby increasing visitors and business branding.

The result of “Ratu Hijab” business plan. First, an attractive and user-friendly website design helps business owners in conveying product information more effectively and efficiently. Second, through website landing pages, hijab products are easier to recognize by visitors and increase visitor conversions. Third, website features such as product catalogs and direct links to social media make it easier for business owners to reach a wider market, increase sales and compete better in the digital era.

Some suggestions for “Ratu Hijab” business owners who can consider the design of the business model that has been recommended from the results of the research and for future researchers, this research is expected to be a reference related to the same problem so that the author’s research can be further perfected carefully.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anggita, S. D. (2023). Utilization of Website-Based Information Systems to Optimize Data Management in Khaela Hijab. *Dinamisia: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 7(1), 1–9.
- [2] Hidayah, R., Farid, E. S., & Adda, H. W. (2023). Penerapan Bisnis Model Kanvas Dalam Upaya Pengembangan Usaha Sweet Banana. *Jurnal EMA*, 8(1), 10–19.
- [3] Khadijah, N., & Iryani, L. (2023). *Implementasi E-Commerce Berbasis Web Sebagai Media Promosi dalam Meningkatkan Penjualan Produk*. 6(2), 245–259.
- [4] Kusuma, Y. B., & Kusumasari, I. R. (2022). Analisis Penerapan Pola Freemium dalam Model Bisnis Aplikasi Steaming Musik Spotify (Studi Kasus Model Bisnis Freemium Pada Aplikasi Spotify). *Jurnal Bisnis Indonesia*, 13(2), 1–10.
- [5] Lailia, V. R., & Dwiridotjahjono, J. (2023). Penerapan Strategi Pemasaran Digital Melalui Media Sosial Instagram Dalam Meningkatkan Penjualan Pada Arunazma. *Jurnal of Management and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 1–10.
- [6] Majir, A. (2021). *Pendidikan Kewirausahaan Teori dan Praktik (Melahirkan Enterpreneurship Handal di Era Industry 4.0 & Society 5.0)*. 1–11. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=nxBNEAAQBAJ>
- [7] Putra, A. I., & Diana, A. (2020). Perancangan E-commerce dengan Business Model Canvas untuk Peningkatan Penjualan pada Toko Parfum. *Jurnal Telematika*, 15(1), 19–28.
- [8] Rakib, M. (2010). Pengaruh Model Komunikasi Wirausaha, Pembelajaran Wirausaha, dan Sikap Kewirausahaan terhadap Kinerja Usaha Kecil. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 2, 121–129.
- [9] Rakib, M., Yunus, M., & Amin MT, N. (2018). Creative Industry Development Based on Entrepreneurship Training in Developing Local Economy in Parepare City. *Jurnal OIKOS*, 2(1), 32–46.
- [10] Rukmana, U. L., & Rohman, A. (2022). Sistem Informasi Berbasis Web pada Penjualan Kerudung Salimah Hijab di Desa Mluweh Ungaran Timur. *Jurnal Mahasiswa Teknik Informatika*, 1(1), 17–28.
- [11] Syam, A., R, R., & Isma, A. (2024). Strategy for Implementing Digital Marketing (Case Study of a Coconut Fruit Expedition Business in Makassar City). *Journal of Applied Business, Taxation and Economics Research*, 3(4), 431–437. <https://doi.org/10.54408/jabter.v3i4.304>
- [12] Yani, I., Rakib, M., & Syam, A. (2020). Pengaruh Literasi Kewirausahaan dan Karakter Wirausaha terhadap Keberhasilan Usaha Kecil. *Journal of Economic Education and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 1(2), 65–77.
- [13] Yusri, A. Z. dan D. (2020). Kewirausahaan. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 7(2), 809–820.